

APPROACHES AND METHODS OF LANGUAGE TEACHING.

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Marguba Nomozova Allonovna

Scientific Supervisor

Axmedjanova Nasiba Ilhomjon qizi

Student

Karshi State University, Karshi

Annotation

This work studies the development of sociolinguistic, linguistic, pragmatic and strategic competence and the importance in language teaching.

Key words

strategic, pragmatic, sociolinguistic, competence.

As we all know that, nowadays, learning foreign languages plays an important role especially in the globalization process. Therefore, we should pay extensive attention earnestly to the young generation's occupation of foreign languages in order to make a tremendous progress in the future. In Uzbekistan, English has been applied for any levels. It has been applied from kindergarten up to college. It means that, English is not something new in our country. Many people use it to communicate each other in daily life. In fact, children also use it to communicate each other, to sing a song (kid songs), and to mention simple something such as numbers, colors, animals, etc. They use it like their first language although, sometime they use it by using bilingual. They are enough brave to practice it. Actually, they are still children but they are easy to memorize something that they ever see and listen it. The classroom has been called the experimental lab of the child. Because children spend a major part of their formative years in school, it becomes vital to examine the roles of classroom management and discipline as an important dynamic in student experience and success. A controlled classroom environment is essential for effective learning, good teacher-pupil relationships, and peer collaboration. Schools that typically have a difficult time establishing and enforcing a discipline policy regularly experience teacher burnout and turnover. Many teachers commonly find that approximately one-half of all classroom time can be taken up with activities other than instruction. It can be very difficult for teachers to receive effective training in the right strategies that will allow them

more instructional time and less management of behavioral troubles. This is a big problem when considering standards-based educational goals and the rising accountability to meet certain target rates of success for schools, teachers, and students. Conversely, districts that enforce a school wide discipline policy help prevent and direct behavior problems by coordinating procedures throughout the school and informing the students extensively of appropriate and inappropriate actions. When teachers do get the right kind of training, real changes can be made in the strategies they use for classroom curriculum instruction and in the organization of basic management approaches. This means more students will be engaged in their learning activities, which will translate to more teaching and learning actually occurring. In fact, discipline is so important that it should be viewed as an extension of the learning process. To facilitate learning, there needs to be order in the classroom. "Order in a classroom simply means that within acceptable limits the students are following the program of action necessary for a particular classroom event to be realized in the situation". To attain this order, teachers must prepare, plan, reflect, and apply effective management strategies, just as they would with every other subject. Linguistic competence refers to the knowledge of grammar and vocabulary. Traditionally, English language teaching focused on mechanical grammar drills. This focus is influenced by the idea that grammar and vocabulary are the basic building blocks of a language. Other aspects of communication, such as culture and interpersonal relationships were neglected in this traditional model.

As we studied at school and then at university we were taught according to Grammar Translation Method. The students were explained the grammar rules, then given sentences for translation from Russian into English or vice versa. We were asked to make up sentences using these grammar rules. As an assessment we were asked these grammar rules. In spite of learning grammar rules by heart, we had difficulties in using them in communication. The word "Facilitator" according to Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary "a person who helps somebody do something more easily by discussing problems, giving advice, etc. rather than telling them what to do" (p.545). A facilitator is a monitor, adviser and teacher and must be a good friend with students.

In the language classroom, teachers should strive to balance form, meaning, and use. Students should understand not only the mechanics of the language, but also the hows, whys, and wheres a particular structure, word, or phrase gets used.

For example, in a lesson on the past perfect tense, students need to learn the sentence structure. The teacher first drills past participles on a variety of verbs (eat

/ eaten, swim / swum, buy / bought). He then plugs the past participles into the grammar structure, with students then further practicing the material via example sentences and more drills.

However, the class also needs to learn that the past perfect places actions or events in order for the listener or reader. The grammar serves as a marker of when events happened. This is especially needed when the speaker forgets some information and has to backtrack in the story. This is also important when information needs further clarification.

Pragmatic competence is the ability to use language effectively in order to achieve a specific purpose and to understand a language in context. Pragmatic competence is a fundamental aspect of a more general communicative competence. Not being pragmatically competent speakers and hearers may not understand each other and not understanding the speaker's words, there may be some misunderstandings. Or for the given question people's answers can be different according to their ages, gender, period of their living, life experience and situation in which they are.

Sociolinguistic competence has been an integral part of communicative competence in that it includes learning pragmatic and sociolinguistic knowledge about how to use language linguistically and socially appropriately. However, a number of studies highlight the lack of such communicative skills among EFL learners regardless of their proficiency level of linguistic knowledge. More specially, learners may not be able to develop socio-pragmatic knowledge of language as much as grammatical knowledge of the language being learnt. Informed by this critical inconsistency and learning challenge, this study reports the perceptions of English teachers about the development of sociolinguistic competence in language classrooms. The purpose is to explore their perceptions about learners' as well as the non-native EFL teachers' knowledge of sociolinguistic competence along with any difficulty they may face with the integration of this particular competence in their classroom practice. Both native (n=35) and non-native (n=35) English teachers were administered a questionnaire and were asked to submit written reports revealing their perceptions underpinning the knowledge and practice of sociolinguistic competence as part of communicative competence. The results revealed that the development of sociolinguistic rules can guide learners in the choice of appropriate forms which should be closely integrated in language teaching and learning curricula. Strategic competence, an aspect of communicative competence, refers to the ability to overcome difficulties when communication breakdowns occur. Rather than viewing communication

breakdowns as a deficit, teachers should take them as an opportunity for learners to develop their strategic competence. Celce-Murcia, Dörnyei and Thurrell (1995) suggest a number of strategies to respond to communication breakdowns. Perhaps the most straightforward strategy is to avoid discussing unfamiliar topics, but this is not always possible. Strategies for identifying whether a breakdown has occurred include paying attention to body language and frequently checking listener comprehension. Knowing that communication breakdowns occur in authentic speech, teachers should prepare learners to respond to such situations. It is important for learners to be aware that communication breakdowns are not uncommon among competent users of English. A sound understanding of communication can prevent learners from feeling discouraged when they encounter communication breakdowns. Teachers can develop and teach language patterns to help prevent and repair breakdowns. For example, the ability to paraphrase what the speaker has said and to ask checking questions is a very useful skill, and one that is very common among competent speakers. One of the ways to draw learners to this feature of authentic communication is to show them recordings of TV interviews and talk shows. Then, learners can identify strategies that interviewees and interviewers use to compensate communication problems. A follow-up activity could be Strategic competence, an aspect of communicative competence, refers to the ability to overcome difficulties when communication breakdowns occur. Rather than viewing communication breakdowns as a deficit, teachers should take them as an opportunity for learners to develop their strategic competence. Celce-Murcia, Dörnyei and Thurrell (1995) suggest a number of strategies to respond to communication breakdowns. Perhaps the most straightforward strategy is to avoid discussing unfamiliar topics, but this is not always possible. Strategies for identifying whether a breakdown has occurred include paying attention to body language and frequently checking listener comprehension. Knowing that communication breakdowns occur in authentic speech, teachers should prepare learners to respond to such situations. It is important for learners to be aware that communication breakdowns are not uncommon among competent users of English. A sound understanding of communication can prevent learners from feeling discouraged when they encounter communication breakdowns. Teachers can develop and teach language patterns to help prevent and repair breakdowns. For example, the ability to paraphrase what the speaker has said and to ask checking questions is a very useful skill, and one that is very common among competent speakers. One of the ways to draw learners to this feature of authentic communication is to show them

recordings of TV interviews and talk shows. Then, learners can identify strategies that interviewees and interviewers use to compensate communication problems. A follow-up activity could be a role play.

The type of classroom activities proposed in CLT also implied new roles in the classroom for teachers and learners. Learners now have to participate in classroom activities that were based on a cooperative rather than individualistic approach to learning. Students have to become comfortable with listening to their peers in group work or pair work tasks, rather than relying on the teacher for a model. They were expected to take on a greater degree of responsibility for their own learning. And teachers now have to assume the role of facilitator and monitor. Rather than being a model for correct speech and writing and one with the primary responsibility of making students produce plenty of error-free sentences, the teacher has to develop a different view of learners' errors and of her/his own role in facilitating language learning.

One of the goals of CLT is to develop fluency in language use. Fluency is natural language use occurring when a speaker engages in meaningful interaction and maintains comprehensible and ongoing communication despite limitations in his or her communicative competence. Fluency is developed by creating classroom activities in which students must negotiate meaning, use communication strategies, correct misunderstandings, and work to avoid communication breakdowns. Fluency practice can be contrasted with accuracy practice, which focuses on creating correct examples of language use. Differences between activities that focus on fluency and those that focus on accuracy can be summarized as follows: Activities focusing on fluency is to reflect natural use of language, focusing on achieving communication, requiring meaningful use of language and communication strategies. Produce language that may not be predictable and seek to link language use to context. Activities focusing on accuracy can be reflecting classroom use of language and focusing on the formation of correct examples of language as well as practicing language out of context and small samples of language.

Today CLT can be seen as describing a set of core principles about language learning and teaching, as summarized above, assumptions which can be applied in different ways and which address different aspects of the processes of teaching and learning. Some focus centrally on the input to the learning process. Thus content-based teaching stresses that the content or subject matter of teaching drives the whole language learning process. Some teaching proposals focus more directly on instructional processes. Task-based instruction for example, advocates the use of

specially designed instructional tasks as the basis of learning. Others, such as competency-based instruction and text-based teaching, focus on the outcomes of learning and use outcomes or products as the starting point in planning teaching. Today CLT continues in its classic form as seen in the huge range of course books and other teaching resources that cite CLT as the source of their methodology. In addition, it has influenced many other language teaching approaches that subscribe to a similar philosophy of language teaching.

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